

Effect of Participation in Agricultural Training on Farmers in Surulere Local Government Area

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Abstract

This study assessed effect of participation in agricultural training on farmers in Surulere Local Government Area. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 100 Farmers in the study area. Data were collected using interview schedule. Descriptive statistical tools and logit model were used. The mean number of years spent in school was 6 years. The coefficient of years of farming experience was positive and significant at 10 percentage level. It was concluded that the highly experienced farmers participate better or more in agricultural training. Therefore, the less experienced farmers should be sensitized on the need to participate better or more in agricultural training.

Keywords: Age, farming experience, household size, participation status and training,

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has played a crucial role in meeting the needs of the world's poor and hungry in rural areas, where a disproportionate number of these people now live. Before the country's oil discovery in 1958 and subsequent expansion in the 1970s, agriculture in Nigeria contributed considerably to GDP (roughly 80%) but was later abandoned (Nlebem & Raji, 2019).

Every organization is being run or operated by human beings. They actually form the building blocks of any business venture, activity and determine the extent of productivity that could be attained by any organization (Onuka et al., 2012). In where farming activities are concerned, the farmers need to be well and sustainably trained if reasonable level of success is to be achieved. The effect of training on farmers cannot be overemphasized as Onuka (2012) reiterated that it helps to guide against accidents in work place (farm), wastage of farm resources and attainment of full potential in production capacity. This accounts for why Salihu (2011) postulated that an organization level of productivity is directly dependent on the level of training its workers have received. Going by the aforementioned, Salihu (2011) advocated the need for steady manpower training in order to ensure good level of productivity. Singh and Mohanty (2012) while supporting the need for farmers to be trained, stated that training is central and a powerful instrument for effective achievement of organizational objectives and goals that is likely to result to greater farm productivity and consequently income.

The skills and knowledge supposedly assumed to be earned by the rural farmers farm training are jeopardized by a myriad of challenges plagued them (Adebayo and Okuneye, 2005). Adebayo and Okuneye, (2005) opined that the farmers need to be organized through collective efforts so that they can overcome the myriads of problems limiting them. Such an organized style or system would lead to farmers participation. Such participation, are a sure means of improving farm practices and consequently their farm income.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study areas;
2. Estimate effect of participation in agricultural training on respondents in the study area

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Surulere Local Government Area, Oyo-State, Nigeria. Its headquarters is in the town of Iresa-Adu. It has an area of 23 km² and a population of 142,070 at the 2006 census (NPC, 2006). The annual growth rate of 3.4% was estimated (National bureau of Statistics, 2018). Therefore, in 2024 the State's population is 229, 016. Some of the towns in the local government are Iresa-Adu, Igbon and Iresa-Apa. The main economic activities of the residents of the towns that make up Surulere local government is farming. The main produce from there farming activity is: Yam, Cocoa, Palm oil, Maize and Tobacco.

The population for this study consisted of all farmers in Surulere Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Multistage sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The first stage was the purposive sampling of four (4) villages. The second stage was the proportionate sampling of 10% of registered famers. Thus, a total of 100 respondents were interviewed.

Descriptive Statistical Tools that were used include frequency counts, percentages, means and Logit model. These were used to describe socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and the effect of participation in agricultural training on respondents. Also, Logit model was used to test for the null hypothesis.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Table 1 illustrates the Socio demographic characteristics of respondents.

Most (60%) of the Farmers were males. The farming is dominated by males. This is probably because; crop is a perennial crop that is usually been inherited by male folks.

The farmers which were less than 40 years of age were 62.00%. Thus, a good number of the respondents were in their youths. The respondents that were within ages of 40 to 44 years and 45 to 49 years were 18.00% and 11.00% respectively. Also, the respondents that were greater than 50 years of age were 7.00%. Therefore, the aged respondents were less than the younger ones. Moreover, the mean age of the respondents was 40 years. This was an indication that the farmers were young, productive and agile. This could enable them to adopt and diffuse innovative technologies and/or training that could improve their production.

The marital status of respondents were single (31.00%), married (66.00%) and divorced (3.00%). The married category were the main category (66.00%). The married status could encourage the use of household members as cheap family laborers to the respondents.

The household size of respondents were 3 (55.00%), 4-6 (34.00%) and > 6 (8.00%). The 3 individuals category was the main category (55.00%) and the mean household size was 4 individuals. This implies that the respondents have very few household members that were depending on them. This could reduce diversion of resource that is meant for farming to household up keeps.

The number of years spent in school were < 7 (67.00%), 7-12 (28.00%) and > 12 (6.00%). The mean number of years spent in school was 6 years. This implies that most of the respondents were mainly primary school leavers. Education could improve adoption of improved training on farming.

Table 1: Socio economic demographic characteristics of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	60	60.00
Female	40	40.00
Age (years)		
<40	62	62.00
40–44	18	18.00
45–49	11	11.00
>50	7	7.00
Mean = 40		
Marital Status		
Single	31	31.00
Married	66	66.00
Divorced	3	3.00
Household size		
3	55	55.00
4-6	34	34.00
> 6	11	11.00
Mean = 4		
Number of years spent in school		
< 7	67	67.00
7-12	28	28.00
> 12	6	6.00
Mean = 6		

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Effect of participation in agricultural training on respondents**Table 2: Relationship between training received by farmers and selected characteristics**

Dependent variable	Independent variables	Coefficient	P> t
Participation in agricultural training			
	Number of years spent in school	-0.356	0.187
	Household size	0.382	0.308
	Years of farming experience	0.494	0.091
	Constant	0.144	0.598

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

In Table 2, effect of participation in agricultural training on respondents was presented. The coefficient of years of farming experience was positive and significant at 10 percentage level. This shows that the highly experienced farmers participate better or more in agricultural training. This was probably because high experience could increase the likelihood of an individual to participate in highly innovative endeavor such as agricultural training.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

It was concluded that farmers were in their productive years. The respondents were not highly educated. The highly experienced farmers participate better or more in agricultural training. It was recommended that young and educated individuals should be encouraged to participate in farming. Government and non-governmental organization should employ more extension agents in other to improve farmers training. The less experienced farmers should be sensitized on the need to participate better or more in agricultural training.

4. REFERENCES

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